

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

**Assoc. Prof Adekunle
Olusola OTUNLA**

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

**Dr Michael
GBADEGESIN**

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

**Dr Emmanuel O.
MALOMO**

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

**Rebecca Oluwatosin
BANJO**

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

**Emmanuel Selome
FASINU**

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

© 2025 Authors

**Assessment of Leadership Styles, Mission
Strategies and Corporate Social
Responsibility (CSR) through
Infrastructural Development in The
Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria 1999-
2019**

Oluwagbenga Emmanuel ADEJORO

*Department of Politics and International Relations
Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead
City University*

Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

emmy2510@gmail.com, +2348036615260

Adekunle Olusola OTUNLA

*Department of Mass Communication and Media
Technology*

*Faculty of Communication and Information
Sciences Lead City University*

Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

otunlad@yahoo.com +2348023354237,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0827-2858>

Abstract

Church growth largely depend on the leadership structure and potentials within the Christiana organisation. Again, leadership styles deployed by hierarchical leaders impact on the attainment of long-term Christian faith experience that also contributes to the overall living conditions and welfare of the people within a Christian organisation and on the long term promotes national productivity. Although there have been substantial completed studies that authenticated what are now considered mainstream leadership styles. However, there seems to be not many of such research on assessment of leadership styles of Christian organizational hierarchical heads in relation to Church Corporate Social Responsibility

(CSR) through infrastructural development. Therefore, this study assessed leadership styles and Church Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through infrastructural development under two General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. The study adopted descriptive survey research design and the sample involve 172 respondents who were randomly selected among the Church hierarchical leaders in the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria. Self-designed and validated instruments were used to collect data for this study; namely: Leadership Styles Adoption Questionnaire (LSAQ) $r=0.976$; Infrastructural Development Adoption Questionnaire (IDAQ) $r=0.961$; and Interview Guide for Organizational Leaders (IGOL). Descriptive statistics was used for data analysis. Findings revealed that the predominant leadership styles exhibited by the two General Overseers were democratic ($\bar{x}= 1.66$) and partially autocratic ($\bar{x}= 2.42$) and their leadership styles impacted positively on the Church CSR through infrastructural development leading to improvements and upgrade of mission educational and institutional buildings; primary and secondary schools ($\bar{x}1.77$); Foursquare hospital ($\bar{x}1.70$), seminary classrooms ($\bar{x}1.95$), establishment of conference ($\bar{x}1.66$) and remodeled worship centers. Other CSR infrastructural development include borehole drilling ($\bar{x}1.68$)and provisions of vocational training facilities ($\bar{x}1.80$). The study concludes that Church CSR under the two General Overseers' leadership styles substantially impacted on Infrastructural development of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. Therefore, the study recommends sustainability and enhancement of the exhibited and deployed leadership styles to further improve on the infrastructural development as CSR that will benefit the lives of the member of the Church and the larger Nigerian public. The study further recommends that Church leaders should be dynamic in the deployment of desirable leadership styles to engender continuity in Church CSR and maintenance of existing infrastructural facilities as this study established the fact that leadership style resonates with infrastructural development.

Keywords: Leadership-style, Welfare, Infrastructural-development, Church-Impact

Introduction

Christian mission organisations are established to pursue pre-conceived goals and objectives in relations to the Great Commission mandate. Mission and vision statements remain potent strategies that can be adopted in order to achieve the mandate of any organization including Christian organisations. Establishment of Church ministries are also geared towards Church Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through provisions of infrastructure development which are regarded as a critical factor in promoting wellbeing of the membership and strengthening followership

within the faith community. Hence, development of Church vision and mission statements are important to everyone involved in any organization, including outside stakeholders, who need to understand what the organization intends to accomplish and how it will be accomplished. (Sposato & Rumens, 2021). Although an organisation will have just one vision statement and one mission statement, but it may have several strategies that serves as pathway on how the organization wish to achieve their mandate. More specifically, a strategy is a unique approach that can be used by Christian missions to achieve their vision. Hence, Olayisade and Awolusi (2021) postulates that strategies are critical to the success of an organisation because this is where the leaders begin to outline a plan of action for doing something or have a general guideline on how the vision will be achieved.

One of the Church organisational strategies in the pursuit of evangelistic and Christian ministries include the execution of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes and projects. Adamolekun and Rotimi (2022) further affirm that traditionally, the African society built social responsibility into their belief system and social relationship. Corporate Social Responsibility is a public relations strategy and a major tool that is synonymous with corporate bodies by providing social responsibility initiatives towards meeting the basic needs of their host communities. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2002) in Adamolekun and Rotimi (2022) defines CSR as ‘The continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as the larger society. The authors while tracing the history of CSR in Nigeria states that perhaps the first concerted efforts at institutionalising social responsibility came with advent of Christian missions to Nigeria. Thus, the earliest Christian mission organisations who came to Nigeria between late 1700 and early 1800 because of the need for evangelism and partly the need for inducing the acceptance of Western civilization; became actively involved in providing education for their adherents in several parts of Nigeria.

Notably, Adamolekun and Rotimi (2022) identifies the frontiers of such missions to include: the Roman Catholic Church Mission, the Anglican Communion (Church of England), the Southern American Baptist (The Ana-Baptist), Wesley Mission, United Middle Belt Church Mission, Methodist Mission, and a host of others. Invariably, the Christian mission

organisations as a way of contributing to CSR of the Nigerian society chatted the way in being socially responsive to the educational and health needs of their members who are majorly converts. Thus, the mission Churches pioneered establishment of Western education and orthodox health institutions in different parts of Nigeria. The authors likewise reported on the efforts of the Muslim missions towards CSR, notable missions include Ahmadiyyah Missions and the Ausar-ud-deen Mission who equally invested in education and health of their members.

Therefore, involvement of faith-based organisation in the provision of corporate social responsibility projects and programmes is not new in Nigeria.

The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria as at inception did not have what can be called a mission policy properly documented, what was available then was the National church planting policy. This policy which aims and objective was to plant Foursquare churches in states capitals of the Federation where no Foursquare churches existed before, which was officially put into effect in 2005 according to a report submitted by Rev. Dr. David Oluwashina, while in office as the Foursquare church, director of missions (Sendjaya, 2002). Hence, the Church document contains the mission focus, objectives and goals (Sendjaya, 2002). How these three (3) ingredients above interact will constitute the mission policy. The document defines the understanding of the great commission. Our understanding of the great commission must be viewed in the light of a mission policy. It should be noted that the understanding and interpretation of the great commission which is supposed to be what will constitute the policy varies from one organization to the other. These will automatically give birth to the following questions before a comprehensive mission policy can be drawn; (a). What do we intend to do and; (b). How do we intend to do it? The answers to these questions were the bases for the formulation of the Church mission policy.

Also, the mission policy cannot and should not be static, methods can change but the message cannot and must not change. Hence, the need to understand the prevailing situation in which the Church find ourselves. The document shows or identifies the specific goals and desires of the Church in the world evangelism and how exactly such desires can be actualised. Since it is not a static document, the document should be periodically reviewed. The document emphasized that the mission must be written in other to help

the Church to achieve a clear sense of direction, maintain consistency, develop a loving accountability in our mission department and also help us to be in better harmony with the rest of the church/organ or activities as the case may be. (Christian, Natalia, Bangun & Hadijah 2022). The authors further states that for a good mission policy, there must be a well constituted “mission Board” which will include the writers of the policy, the interpreters of the policy and the executors of the policy document.

Mission practices in The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria from history have always seen driven by the General Overseer’s office. After the emergence of indigenization era which was swift and steady, brought about thirty (30) churches. Hence, the first era of the indigenization saw The Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria coming out of the woods into limelight through the dynamic ministry of preaching of Rev. Sam Odunaike. The church was seen as becoming a strong youth church. The ministry of Rev. Paul Jinadu was also a magnetic one in Ibadan then drawing a lot of young people to the Lord with great zeal to serve the Lord and who hunger for the truth.

Leaders are people who are able to make judgments affecting the future of others or who are able to make decisions regarding the business model of their organizations, corporations, or institutions on their own are referred to as leaders. Thus, leadership may be defined as a mix of character and responsibility, with the goal of saving individuals and organizations and setting things on the correct path (Idowu, 2020; Thompson, Buch, Thompson, & Glaso, 2021). Leadership is one of the key determinants associated with the success or failure of any organization. Adunola (2022) conducted a study that focused on leadership styles: transformational, transactional, autocratic, charismatic, bureaucratic, and democratic. The findings suggested that charismatic, bureaucratic, and transactional leadership styles have negative relationships with organizational performance. Transformational, autocratic, and democratic leadership styles on the other hand, had a positive relationship with organizational performance.

Olofinjana and Religion (2021) highlighted the necessity for academics to investigate the influence of different leadership styles, such as transformational, transactional, and servant leadership, on the service behaviour of employees and, ultimately, the effect the behaviour has on the quality of the service that is provided. However, there are academics who

have emphasized the importance of researching leadership styles based on the cultural characteristics of a country. It is due to the fact that other countries have cultural characteristics that are clearly distinct from those of the west, which may influence leadership styles. The author therefore, investigated the impact that a paternalistic leadership style (Paternalistic leadership is a style where the leader acts as a "father figure," prioritizing employee well-being and making decisions on their behalf, expecting loyalty and obedience in return, often creating a family-like atmosphere) has on the service behaviour of employees and, as a result, the quality of service provided by small indigenous organisation in Nigeria.

A conceptual model was developed that links paternalistic leadership to customer contact employee service behaviours. This model was underpinned by both theories of social exchange and reasoned action. This model was put to the test using structural equation modelling on a sample of 95 customer contact organisation employees and 104 customers in Nigeria (Idowu, 2020). Findings revealed that paternalistic leadership, which is the predominant leadership style in Nigerian organisations, due to the cultural characteristics of Nigeria, has no effect on the service behaviour of customer contact employees and, as a result, has no impact on the quality of service provided to customers. This runs counter to the idea that leadership styles should be aligned with the cultural norms and values of a society. Because of the effects of globalization on people's expectations of how they should be led, Nigerian societies are gradually transitioning from a cultural dynamic that is totally traditional to one that is more modern (Olofinjana & Religion, 2021).

Transformational leadership is a very effective leadership style and both academic and project practitioner literature advocate it for project management. In order to gain a deeper understanding of effective leadership processes with the goal of boosting work engagement, Omodunbi, Akinrinde, Ige and Olawole (2021) investigated the relationship between social identity and transformational leadership. A case study using a qualitative technique and three research questions were constructed using a social constructionist epistemology. Twenty semi-structured interviews sector workers resulted in the collection of data. By analysing the data and creating topics, a thematic analysis was carried out. Findings revealed that transformational leadership behaviours foster social identity in project teams, which increases worker engagement, how project governance affects

leadership, and how leadership effectiveness can be assessed and potentially enhanced. The research has been conceptualized within a leadership framework and offers new, significant insights that advance both theoretical understanding and project management practice. Additionally, restrictions are noted, and potential areas for further investigation were (Omodunbi, Akinrinde, Ige & Olawole, 2021).

Wadibia (2022), reported on the leadership roles of the Church, citing one of Nigeria's most popular, richest, and politically influential indigenous Pentecostal Church as largely responsible for establishing the church into the global religious movement that it is today. Currently, the church invests in a variety of development causes in Nigeria to compensate for the state's inadequate development institutions and to serve its Nigerian development goal. This author contended among other things, that the church has been involved in the establishment of a tiered higher education investment model and that a theological softening has occurred, inspiring the church to identify biomedicine as spiritually acceptable. The author concluded by comparing the RCCG's perspective of development to that of other significant Pentecostal groups in Nigeria and around the world, as well as discussing what the study's findings indicate for broader discussions about third generation Pentecostalism (Wadibia, 2022). The present study therefore assessed influence of Leadership Style on Infrastructural Development of General Overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria 1999-2019.

Statement of the Problem

Church Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through diversified mission strategies and infrastructure development is regarded as a critical factor in promoting wellbeing of the membership and strengthening followership within the faith community. Church growth largely depend on the leadership structure and potentials within the Christiana organisation. Hence, the assessment of leadership infrastructural development can have different immediate and futuristic implications for any organization, Leadership is one of the key determinants associated with the success or failure of any organization. Again, leadership styles deployed by hierarchical leaders impact on the attainment of long-term Christian faith experience that also contributes to the overall living conditions and welfare

of the people within a Christian organisation and on the long term promotes national productivity.

Further, Church organisations are well-known to be significant participants and vehicles in the process of encouraging human progress and communities' transformation under various leaderships leading to societal development. Scholars have been studying various aspects of development issues for many decades and there has been substantial completed studies that authenticated what are now considered mainstream leadership styles. However, there seems to be not many of such research on assessment of leadership styles of Christian organizational hierarchical heads in relation to Church Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through infrastructural development. Therefore, this study assessed leadership styles and Church Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through infrastructural development under two General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019.

Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to assess leadership styles and Church Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through infrastructural development under two General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. The objectives are to:

1. ascertain the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019.
2. assess the influence of Leadership Styles of the General overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria on the Mission Strategies adoption of Church between 1999-2019.
3. assess the influence of leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the Church infrastructural developments between 1999-2019?

Research Questions

1. What are the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019?
2. What is the influence of Leadership Styles of the General overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria on the Mission Strategies adoption of Church between 1999-2019?

-
3. What is the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the Church infrastructural developments between 1999-2019?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. This design affords the researcher the opportunity to gather data from a large sample within the study coverage through Church Leaders and Administrative Officers of the Organisation. The estimated population was 220 which include National Executive Council (NEC) members and some administrative Officers at the National Office. The study adopted multistage sampling procedure. Firstly, purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the respondents who are leaders in the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria. A total of 172 respondents were selected. Furthermore, the study also adopted stratified sampling technique to select twelve (12) nominated Leaders that served as key informant respondents who were interviewed who had served for at least 40 years with the Organisation. Two (2) validate questionnaire and one interview guide were design to elicit data for this study. The instruments are: Leadership Styles Adoption Questionnaire ($r = 0.76$). Mission Strategies Adoption Questionnaire ($r = 0.82$) and Interview Guide for Organization Leaders ($\alpha = 0.69$). Table 1 provides further details.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender, Age, Marital Status and Highest Educational Qualification (N=172)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	153	89.0
Female	19	11.0
Age		
Below 25years	5	3.0
30-40years	7	4.0
40-45years	3	2.0
45-50years	18	11.0
50-60years	71	41.0
61years and Above	68	39.0
Marital Status		
Single	12	7.0
Married	156	91.0
Widow	2	1.0
Widower	2	1.0
Highest Educational Qualification		
Primary Six	10	6.0
WASC/SSCE	8	5.0
Sub-degree e.g. ND, NCE Certificate	5	3.0
Degree/HND	56	32.0
Master Degree	57	33.0
D.Min/PhD	36	21.0

Source: Field Work, 2023

Result and Discussion of Findings

Research Question One: What are the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019?

Table 2: Leadership Styles Adopted by the General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria between 1999-2019 (N=172)

Items on Democratic Leadership Style	HA	A	NA	Mean	SD				
Consider the needs of the organisation in the execution of the vision	107	62%	58	34%	7	4%	1.42	0.57	
Created an enabling environment for teamwork	77	45%	82	48%	13	7%	1.63	0.62	
Acknowledged, appreciated and gave due credit to the support of the workers	75	44%	78	45%	19	11%	1.67	0.67	
Put the options of the people into consideration	65	38%	74	43%	33	19%	1.81	0.73	
Handled conflicts effectively without injustice	67	39%	79	46%	26	15%	1.76	0.69	
Promoted a strong partnership between the leader and the led	63	37%	98	57%	11	6%	1.70	0.58	
Encouraged transparency in the leader-led relationship	80	46%	77	45%	15	9%	1.62	0.64	
Were accountable for decisions and actions	71	41%	88	51%	13	8%	1.66	0.61	
					Weighted		1.66	0.63	
Mean									
Items on Autocratic Leadership Style	HA	A	NA	Mean	SD				
Made irrevocable decisions even when it was disadvantageous to the members of the organization	42	24%	56	33%	74	43%	2.19	0.80	
Prevented interpersonal relationship with the members of the organisation	25	15%	43	25%	104	60%	2.46	0.74	
Imposed their vision on the members in the organisation without consultation and proper consideration	24	14%	47	27%	101	59%	2.45	0.73	
Prevented workers/members from expressing themselves through their rigidity	26	15%	53	31%	93	54%	2.39	0.74	
Accepted no input from workers/members in the organization	22	13%	32	19%	118	68%	2.56	0.71	
Promoted a structure that encouraged monotony	27	16%	41	24%	104	60%	2.45	0.75	
					Weighted		2.42	0.75	
Mean									
Items on Laissez-faire Leadership Style	HA	A	NA	Mean	SD				
Provided little guidance to the members	22	13%	48	28%	102	59%	2.47	0.71	
Expected people to solve their own problems	19	11%	62	36%	91	53%	2.42	0.68	
Took responsibility for overall actions and decisions	60	35%	82	48%	30	17%	1.83	0.70	
Gave members the ability to make decisions	47	27%	89	52%	36	21%	1.94	0.69	
Took charge only when necessary	51	30%	64	37%	57	33%	2.03	0.79	
Provided a creative environment that promoted variety	55	32%	80	47%	37	21%	1.90	0.73	
					Weighted		2.09	0.71	
Mean									

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork 2023

Table 2 reveals that six out of eight items used to measure the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (1.66). For instance, on the item which stated that: Acknowledged, appreciated and gave due credit to the support of the workers ($\bar{x} = 1.67$), Put the options of the people into consideration ($\bar{x} = 1.81$), Handled conflicts effectively without injustice ($\bar{x} = 1.76$), Promoted a strong partnership between the leader and the led ($\bar{x} = 1.70$), Encouraged transparency in the leader-led relationship ($\bar{x} = 1.62$) and Were accountable for decisions and actions ($\bar{x} = 1.66$).

However, items (1 and 2 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set benchmark. This result indicates that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria used democratic leadership style between 1999-2019 since the number of items that are having mean above the benchmark is greater than those who have mean below.

Table 2 shows the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. To answer research question one, the weighted mean (2.42) was determined for the section on autocratic leadership style and taken as benchmark for the explanation of the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. The table reveals that four out of six items used to measure the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (2.42).

For instance, on the item which stated that: Prevented interpersonal relationship with the members of the organisation ($\bar{x} = 2.46$), Imposed their vision on the members in the organisation without consultation and proper consideration ($\bar{x} = 2.45$), Accepted no input from workers/members in the organisation ($\bar{x} = 2.56$), Promoted a structure that encouraged monotony ($\bar{x} = 2.45$), However, items (1 and 4 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set benchmark. This result indicates that General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria used autocratic leadership style between 1999-2019 since the number of items that are having mean above the benchmark is greater than those who have mean below.

Table 2 shows the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. To answer research

question one, the weighted mean (2.09) was determined for the section on laissez-faire leadership style and taken as bench mark for the explanation of the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. The table reveals that three out of six items used to measure the leadership styles adopted by the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria in 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (2.09), for instance, on the item which stated that: Provided little guidance to the members ($\bar{x} = 2.47$), expected people to solve their own problems ($\bar{x} = 2.42$). However, items (3, 4, 5 and 6 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark.

In summary, finding for research question one revealed that the predominant leadership styles adopted by the two General Overseers of The Foursquare Church Nigeria between 1999-2019 were majorly democratic ($x = 1.66$) and partially autocratic ($x = 2.47$, $x = 42$) leadership styles respectively; while they both averagely adopted Laissez- leadership style.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of Leadership Styles of the General overseer of The Foursquare Gospel Church Nigeria on the Mission Strategies adoption of Church between 1999-2019?

Table 3a: Influence of Leadership Styles of the General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the Mission Strategies Adoption of the Church between 1999-2019 (N=172)

Leadership Style on the Mission Strategies:	HA	%	A	%	NA	%	Mean	SD
Medical services, treatment and provision of drugs	63	(37%)	77	(45%)	32	(18%)	1.82	0.72
Food supplies and feeding during festive period	77	(45%)	74	(43%)	21	(12%)	1.67	0.68
Vocational development	56	(33%)	88	(51%)	28	(16%)	1.84	0.68
Establishment of Foursquare National Evangelists	102	(59%)	60	(35%)	10	(6%)	1.47	0.61
Establishment of television station	97	(56%)	56	(33%)	19	(11%)	1.55	0.69
Establishment of schools, colleges and university	85	(50%)	76	(44%)	11	(6%)	1.57	0.61
Establishment of hospitals, guest house and conference center	80	(47%)	72	(42%)	20	(11%)	1.65	0.68
Establishment of College of Theology	92	(54%)	71	(41%)	9	(5%)	1.52	0.59
Water supply	65	(38%)	92	(54%)	15	(8%)	1.71	0.62
Weighted Mean							1.64	0.65

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3b: Influence of Leadership Styles of the General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the Mission Strategies Adoption of the Church between 1999-2019 (N=172)

	HA	%	A	%	NA	%	Mean	SD
Financial support scheme/interest-free loan scheme	70	(41%)	60	(35%)	42	(24%)	1.84	0.79
Distribution of Bible and Christian materials/literature	55	(32%)	79	(46%)	38	(22%)	1.90	0.73
Grace power night	101	(59%)	57	(33%)	14	(8%)	1.49	0.64
Correctional home fellowship	62	(36%)	83	(48%)	27	(16%)	1.80	0.69
Educational support services	56	(33%)	84	(49%)	32	(18%)	1.86	0.70
Youth empowerment	54	(31%)	94	(55%)	24	(14%)	1.83	0.65
Vacation Bible school	56	(33%)	98	(57%)	18	(10%)	1.79	0.62
Holy Spirit refreshing vigil	116	(67%)	49	(29%)	7	(4%)	1.37	0.56
Distribution of clothing materials	64	(37%)	88	(51%)	20	(12%)	1.74	0.65
Prison visitation	58	(34%)	105	(61%)	9	(5%)	1.72	0.56
Pastoral Training Scheme	87	(51%)	79	(46%)	6	(3%)	1.53	0.57
Weighted Mean							1.71	0.65

To answer research question two, the weighted mean (1.68) was determined and taken as bench mark for the explanation of influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 1999-2019. Table 3 shows the influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 1999-2019. The finding revealed that eleven out of twenty items used to measure the influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) same and above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark ($\bar{x}=1.68$). For instance, the items recorded as follows: Medical services, treatment and provision of drugs ($\bar{x} = 1.82$), vocational development ($\bar{x} = 1.84$), water supply ($\bar{x} = 1.71$), educational support services ($\bar{x} = 1.86$), youth empowerment ($\bar{x} = 1.83$), vacation Bible School ($\bar{x} = 1.79$), distribution of clothing materials ($\bar{x} = 1.74$) and prison visitation ($\bar{x} = 1.72$). However, items (6, 7, 8, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark.

The finding indicates that of General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 was impactful on medical services, treatment and provision of drugs, vocational development, water supply, financial support scheme/interest-free loan scheme, distribution of bible and Christian materials/literature, correctional home fellowship, educational support services, youth empowerment, vacation bible school, distribution of clothing materials and prison visitation respectively.

In summary, finding revealed that majority have been on Church planting for years. The respondents were of the opinion that welfare of the worker is not effective. Yes, but was not obvious, the welfare of workers has always been a challenge, but was in more challenges during Decade of multiplication because of argumentation and another person said it was not handled effectively at all. The respondents were of the opinions that the members of the organization are put into consideration in church planting. The respondents were of the opinion that Church planting has been their delight, they had planted over 4 churches. That the major challenges facing Church planting as element of mission are: funding / personnel, man power / financial, community hostility people apathy to church planting, funding,

man power and discourage, personnel, finance human resources lack of finance and man power. Resources has never been is abundance for Church planting. It has always been with struggle, Church planting as by faith assignment it has never been abundance. It has always been with struggle. However, the respondents were of the opinion that people usually participate fully in Church Planting exercise.

Furthermore, to answer research question two, the weighted mean (1.68) was determined and taken as bench mark for the explanation of influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 1999-2019. Table 4 shows the influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseer of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 1999-2019. Again, the table revealed that eleven out of twenty items used to measure the influence of the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the mission strategies adoption of the Church in 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) same and above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark ($\bar{x}=1.68$). For instance, the items recorded as follows: Medical services, treatment and provision of drugs ($\bar{x} = 1.82$), vocational development ($\bar{x} = 1.84$), water supply ($\bar{x} = 1.71$), educational support services ($\bar{x} = 1.86$), youth empowerment ($\bar{x} = 1.83$), vacation Bible School ($\bar{x} = 1.79$), distribution of clothing materials ($\bar{x} = 1.74$) and prison visitation ($\bar{x} = 1.72$). However, items (6, 7, 8, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark. The finding indicates that of General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 was impactful on medical services, treatment and provision of drugs, vocational development, water supply, financial support scheme/interest-free loan scheme, distribution of bible and Christian materials/literature, correctional home fellowship, educational support services, youth empowerment, vacation bible school, distribution of clothing materials and prison visitation respectively.

In summary, the finding on research question two revealed that majority have been on Church planting for years. The respondents were of the opinion that welfare of the worker is not effective. Yes, but was not obvious, the welfare of workers has always been a challenge, but was in more challenges during Decade of multiplication because of argumentation and

another person said it was not handled effectively at all. The respondents were of the opinions that the members of the organization are put into consideration in church planting. The respondents were of the opinion that Church planting has been their delight, they had planted over 4 churches. That the major challenges facing Church planting as element of mission are: funding / personnel, man power / financial, community hostility people apathy to church planting, funding, man power and discourage, personnel, finance human resources lack of finance and man power. Resources has never been is abundance for Church planting. It has always been with struggle, Church planting as by faith assignment it has never been abundance. It has always been with struggle. However, the respondents were of the opinion that people usually participate fully in Church planting exercise.

Research Question Three: What is the leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on the Church infrastructural developments between 1999-2019?

Table 4: Influence of Leadership Styles of the General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria on Infrastructural Development between 1999-2019 (N=172)

Leadership Style on The Mission Strategies	HI	MI	NI	Mean	SD
Building of summary classroom	54 (31%)	72 (42%)	46 (27%)	1.95	0.76
Building of more churches	93 (54%)	68 (40%)	11 (6%)	1.52	0.62
Creation of more zones	111 (65%)	53 (30%)	8 (5%)	1.40	0.58
Creation of more district	113 (66%)	47 (27%)	12 (7%)	1.41	0.62
Upgrade of church building	75 (44%)	82 (48%)	15 (8%)	1.65	0.64
Establishment of Foursquare Barley Harvest Radio	112 (65%)	44 (26%)	16 (9%)	1.44	0.66
Building of primary and secondary schools	71 (41%)	70 (41%)	31 (18%)	1.77	0.74
Creation of more axis and regions	108 (63%)	53 (31%)	11 (6%)	1.44	0.61
Building of Foursquare Hospital	81 (47%)	62 (36%)	29 (17%)	1.70	0.74
Establishment of Conference center	79 (46%)	73 (42%)	20 (12%)	1.66	0.68
Development of Camp facilities	97 (56%)	65 (38%)	10 (6%)	1.49	0.61
Guest Houses	83 (48%)	75 (44%)	14 (8%)	1.60	0.64
Building of Mission schools	64 (37%)	91 (53%)	17 (10%)	1.73	0.63
Borehole Drilling	69 (40%)	89 (52%)	14 (8%)	1.68	0.62
Vocational Training Facilities	55 (32%)	97 (56%)	20 (12%)	1.80	0.63
Weighted Mean				1.62	0.65

Source: Field work, 2023

Table 4 shows the level of infrastructural performance in The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. To answer research question on this variable, the weighted mean (1.62) was determined and taken as bench mark for the explanation of the level of infrastructural performance of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019. The table reveals that eight out of fifteen items used to measure the level of infrastructural performance The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria between 1999-2019 are having mean (\bar{x}) above the weighted mean taken as the benchmark (1.62). For instance, on the item which stated that: Building of summary classroom ($\bar{x} = 1.95$), Upgrade of church building ($\bar{x} = 1.65$), Building of primary and secondary schools ($\bar{x} = 1.77$), Building of Foursquare Hospital ($\bar{x} = 1.70$), Establishment of Conference center ($\bar{x} = 1.66$), Building of Mission schools ($\bar{x} = 1.73$), Borehole Drilling ($\bar{x} = 1.68$) and Vocational Training Facilities ($\bar{x} = 1.80$), However, items (2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 11 and 12 (\bar{x}) means respectively) are below the set bench mark.

In summary, finding on research question three indicated that The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria General Overseers' Leadership Styles impacted on building of seminary classroom, upgrade of church building, building of primary and secondary schools, building of foursquare hospital, establishment of conference centre, building of mission schools, borehole drilling and vocational training facilities receptively between 1999-2019.

Discussion of Findings

The finding is not at variance with author in a study on the influence of leadership styles on employees' performance: a study of Turkana County, Kenya, leadership was described as key to good performance since it coordinates both utilization of human and other resources in the organization (Petriglieri, 2020). The study argues that a good leader motivates employees, and motivated employees do not only increase their job performance and commitment within an organization but also go beyond the job requirements, thus increasing the organization's general performance and making it more profitable. The study further reported that there is no perfect leadership style but according to this study the following leadership styles influenced employee's performance. Affiliation leadership 49.5%, authoritative leadership style 52.2% of employees' performance and therefore it was concluded that the two leadership styles influence county

government employees' style in Turkana County. A research study evaluated the impact of several leadership styles, namely transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and genuine leadership, on the behaviour of travel agents. Authentic leadership has a considerable influence not just on the culture of a business but also on the innovative behaviour of its employees. Transactional leadership had no significant influence on innovative behaviour despite having a strong impact on corporate culture.

Again, findings revealed a positive impact of General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria leadership style as determinant of mission strategies adoption of the Church, support the assertion and discoveries of authors and researchers. For instance, the finding support (Ivanov & Das, 2020) who asserted that over time, religion and politics have converged to become two sides of the same coin. (Ivanov & Das, 2020). This is especially true across the entirety of Africa, including Nigeria, as a direct result of the character of the colonialism that accompanied the advent of the Christian faith. No matter how they were formed, the actions of the numerous missionary organizations that came with colonialism brought about progress in all aspects of life in Nigeria, but especially in the educational sector. This can be demonstrated by the large number of schools that were established by Christian missionaries. These schools have been a source of high-calibre education for many generations, both during and after the time that the country was ruled by colonial powers.

The finding also revealed that The Foursquare Gospel Church has made significant breakthroughs towards Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) with regards to financial contributions to the mission education. The finding aligns with Adamolekun and Rotimi (2022) submission on the laudable contributions of pioneer Christian missionary organizational leaders in Nigeria, and now taken over by the indigenous Christian organisational hierarchical leaders. These contributions have taken the form of the establishment of higher educational institutions as well as chains of secondary and primary schools located throughout Nigeria. These institutions have been responsible for the education of a large number of Nigerians, who have in turn contributed to the nation's economic growth. When compared to the education that was offered by the early Christian missionaries.

Conclusion

Without any outa of contradictions, leadership may be defined as a mix of character and responsibility and organizational leaders are people who are saddled with the responsibilities of taking decisions to derive an organization towards the attainment of the organizational goals; their leadership styles and judgments in a way affects the overall performance and the future of the organisations, corporations or institutions. Conclusion that could be drawn from this study in relation to leadership styles and church corporate social responsibility (CSR) through mission strategies and infrastructural development under two General Overseers of The Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria infers that there is a significant relationship and effectiveness between leadership styles of the General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church and mission strategies and Church infrastructural developments especially, between 1999-2019.

because more laudable achievements were recorded through the Church's CSR programmes and projects; including improvement in schools building, worship centres and provision of hospital. Thus, the authors concludes that effective development of leadership styles could greatly enhance mission strategies and bring about substantial infrastructural development not only in the Church but also in the society in the form of CSR.

Recommendations

The study recommend as follows:

1. Church leaders' sustainability and enhancement of the exhibited and deployed leadership styles to further improve on the Church CSR through infrastructural development as it will benefit the lives of the member of the Church and the larger Nigerian public.
2. Church leaders should be dynamic in the deployment of desirable leadership styles to engender continuity in Church CSR and maintenance of existing infrastructural facilities as this study established the fact that leadership style resonates with infrastructural development.
3. General Overseers of the Foursquare Gospel Church, Nigeria should ensure sustainability of infrastructural development through execution of more social amenities in the Church and the hosting communities.

References

- Adunola T.B, (2022). Leadership styles and their outcomes: a study of a Nigerian hospital middle management nurses. *Leadership in Health Services*, (ahead-of-print).
- Adamolekun, Wole & Rotimi, Olatunji (2022) *Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development*. Lagos: Malhouse Press Limited. Pp 9-25
- Christian, A, Natalia L, Bangun. J.A & Hadijah S. (2022). *Toward A Christian Transformational Leadership*. *Manna Rafflesia*, 9, (1):53-64. ISSN: 2356-4547.
- Idowu. S.A. (2020). Impact of Leadership Styles on Employees' Work Performance in Some South-Western Nigerian Private Universities *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 29(1):100-112.
- Ivanov, D. & Das. A. (2020). Coronavirus (COVID-19/SARS-CoV-2) and supply chain resilience: A research note. *International Journal of Integrated Supply Management*, 13(1):90-102.
- Kiker, D.S, Callahan, J.S. & Kiker, M.B. (2019). Exploring the boundaries of servant leadership: A meta-analysis of the main and moderating effects of servant leadership on behavioral and affective outcomes. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 31(2):172-117.
- Olayisade, A. & Awolusi O. D, (2021), The Effect of Leadership Styles on Employee's Productivity in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry. *Information Management and Business Review*, 13(1 (D)), 47-64.
- Olofinjana, I.O. & Religion T, (2021). Intercultural Reverse Missiology: Towards an African British Contextual Theology (Doctoral dissertation, University of Roehampton),
- Omodunbi, O. O, Akinrinde, O. O, Ige, R. & Olawole, O, (2021) Religious Bodies as Catalyst for National Development in Africa: The Case of the Living Faith Church. *Unnes Political Science Journal*, 5(2): 36-41.
- Petriglieri, G. (2020). The psychology behind effective crisis leadership. *Harvard Business Review*, 22.
- Sendjaya, S. (2002). Servant Leadership: Its Origin, Development, and application in Organizations. *Journal of Leadership and organization studies*.
- Sposato, M. & Rumens, N. (2021). Advancing International Human Resource Management Scholarship on Paternalistic Leadership and Gender: the contribution of postcolonial feminism. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(6): 1201-1221.
- Thompson, G. Buch, R. Thompson, P. M. M. & Glaso, L. (2021). The impact of Transformational Leadership and Interactional Justice on follower Performance and Organizational commitment in a business context. *Journal of General Management*, 46(4): 274-283.

Wadibia, C, (2022). Pentecostalism, Politics, and Development in Nigeria: Understanding Investment in Nigerian Development in the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG). Doctoral dissertation, Faculty of Divinity, University of Cambridge.